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public class HotelBooking {

    static class Room {
        int roomNumber;
        String guestName;
        double pricePerNight;

        Room(int num, double price) {
            this.roomNumber = num;
            this.pricePerNight = price;
            this.guestName = null;
        }

        @Override
        public String toString() {
            String status = (guestName == null) ? "Empty" : "Occupied by " +
guestName;
            return "Room " + roomNumber + " (" + status + ")";
        }
    }

    private List<Room> rooms;

    public HotelBooking(int totalRooms) {
        rooms = new ArrayList<>();
        for (int i = 1; i <= totalRooms; i++) {
            rooms.add(new Room(100 + i, 99.00));
        }
    }

    public boolean checkIn(String name) {
        for (Room r : rooms) {
            if (r.guestName == null) {
                r.guestName = name;
                System.out.println("Check-in successful: " + name + " -> " +
r.roomNumber);
                return true;
            }
        }
        System.out.println("No rooms available for " + name);
        return false;
    }

    public boolean checkOut(String name) {
        for (Room r : rooms) {

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        if (name.equals(r.guestName)) {
            r.guestName = null;
            System.out.println("Check-out successful: " + name);
            return true;
        }
    }
    System.out.println("Guest not found: " + name);
    return false;
}

public void printStatus() {
    int occupied = 0;
    for (Room r : rooms) {
        if (r.guestName != null) occupied++;
    }
    System.out.println("Hotel Status: " + occupied + "/" + rooms.size() + "
occupied.");
}

public static void main(String[] args) {
    HotelBooking hotel = new HotelBooking(3);

    hotel.checkIn("Alice");
    hotel.checkIn("Bob");

    hotel.checkOut("Alice");
    hotel.checkIn("Charlie");

    hotel.printStatus();
}
}
```